

Determination of Aluminium in Water through Formation of Fluorescent Dibenzoylmethane-Aluminium Complex and its Structure Elucidation[†]

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Dibenzoylmethane (DBM) was found to be a very good reagent for Al^{III} to produce a luminescent complex having the formula Al(DBM)₃. The luminescence property of the complex was used to selectively quantify Al^{III} on filter paper substrate in the range of 5–55 ppm. The method was successfully applied to water analysis and is devoid of interferences from common anions and cations.

A survey of recent literature showed varied types of determination techniques for aluminium in trace and ultra-trace levels, viz. fluorimetry¹, spectrophotometry², graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry³, flow injection spectrophotometry⁴, chromatography⁵ and nuclear magnetic resonance spectrometry⁶.

In the present work we have exploited the complexing ability⁷ of dibenzoylmethane (DBM), a well-studied reagent to the formation of a fluorescent aluminium complex. Complete structure elucidation was made by a detailed spectral analysis of the ligand and the complex and this showed 1 : 3 complexation. This was also authenticated from thermogravimetry and elemental analysis of the complex. The formation, extraction and chromatographic separation of the complexes followed by solid surface luminescence detection provided a very simple and sensitive determination procedure for aluminium.

Results and Discussion

Dibenzoylmethane (**1a**) does not have any fluorescence in ethanolic solution, but its complex with Al^{III} (**1b**) shows a deep blue fluorescence (λ_{em} 425; λ_{ex} 370 nm). This complex can either be isolated when produced in larger quantity or can be extracted for *in situ* determination of Al^{III} at lower level. The stoichiometry of this complex was found

to be 1 : 3 (Al : DBM). This was also evidenced from its thermogravimetry and elemental analysis. The neutral character of the complex was ascertained from the conductance measurement (in DMF). The complex showed an absorption maximum at 347 nm (ϵ : 6.92×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹).

¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra : ¹H nmr spectrum shows that the ligand exists exclusively in the enolic form⁸. The appearance of a sharp singlet at δ 6.87 is due to the olefinic proton. The four *ortho*-aromatic protons (H-2,6,2',6') appear as the most downfield broad doublet at δ 8.03 (*J* 10 Hz). The other aromatic protons appear as a multiplet at δ 7.47–7.57.

¹H nmr spectrum of Al(DBM)₃ shows signals at δ 6.94 (C²H), 8.02 (d, *J* 10 Hz, H-2',6',2'',6'') and 7.26–7.46 (m, H-3',4',5',3'',4'',5''). The integration shows the presence of above protons in the ratio of 1 : 4 : 6.

¹³C nmr chemical shifts for the ligand and complex are also in conformity. The presence of two quaternary carbons at δ 184.80 (C¹, C³) and 138.52 (C-1', 1''), four methine carbons at δ 94.14 (C²), 127.90, 128.20 and 131.55 (C-2',6',2'',6''; C-3',5',3'',5'' and C-4',4'') can be rationalised as compared to structurally similar compounds⁹. For DBM the aromatic methine carbons appeared at δ 127.81, 129.03 and 133.35, the carbonyl carbon at 185.05, the olefinic carbon at 92.8 and the aromatic quaternary carbon at 135.03.

Mass spectra : Mass spectrum for the ligand DBM shows usual fragmentation pattern with major peaks at *m/z* (rel. int.) 224 (56.8; M⁺), 223 (61.2), 147 (43.9), 105 (88.9), 77 (88.2), 69 (100) and 51 (45.6). The spectrum for the complex shows molecular ion peak (M⁺) at *m/z* 696 (0.01). This was followed by the elimination of one ligand moiety with the formation of the fragment showing peak at *m/z* 473 (70.5). Further fragmentations obtained were due to the ligand as expected.

Infrared spectra : The ligand shows ir bands at 3059 (aromatic C–H), 2600 (chelated OH), 1534 and 1471

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(aromatic C=C) and 750 cm^{-1} (substituted benzene). The spectrum of $\text{Al}(\text{DBM})_3$, however, showed many of the above bands along with some new bands among which the most prominent being at 419 cm^{-1} for metal-oxygen bond.

Thermal analysis : The complex (5 mg) was heated at the rate of $5^\circ/\text{min}$ in the thermal analyzer. The first and final decompositions were recorded at 240 and 470° . The thermogravimetric curve shows a steady horizontal plateau upto 240° indicating the thermal stability of the chelate and may be used for gravimetric determination of Al. The decomposition of the compound starts at $\sim 245^\circ$, very rapid upto 410° and becoming slow thereafter. The combustion of carbon is then ensued and finished between 450 and 470° . The final weight-loss of 85.36% is in good agreement with the formula. The DTA curve indicates that oxidative degradation of the sample takes place in two stages, authenticated by two exothermic peaks at $245\text{--}450^\circ$ and $450\text{--}470^\circ$, the final product being Al_2O_3 .

Solid surface fluorimetric determination of Al^{III} : Separation of ligand was necessary because it had a quenching effect on the fluorescence of the complex. In order to achieve simplicity and sensitivity, the separation was manifested using paper chromatography with subsequent solid surface luninescence detection. From the calibration graph a linear relationship in the range of $5\text{--}55$ ppm was obtained between the Al^{III} concentration and the fluorescence intensity. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.990, and relative standard deviation $\pm 3\%$.

Real sample analysis : The recommended procedure when applied to the determination of Al^{III} concentration in water samples afforded very good result (Table 1). The results showed good correlation with the values obtained from other method, even in the presence of large amounts naturally occurring anions.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF ALUMINIUM IN WATER SAMPLES

Water type (filtered)	Al present* ppm	Al found** ppm	Relative error %
Tap water (ground water)	5.4	5.3	-0.18
Lake water (III) (Kharagpur campus)	4.9	5.0	+2.00
River water (Kangshaboti)	3.7	4.0	+8.1

*Analysed by AAS (electrothermal). **Average of 3 determinations.

Interference study : The effects of diverse ions including nonquenching metal ions like Be^{II} , Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and alkali metal ions were tested. Ten-fold excess of Be^{II} , 15-fold excess of Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} and 100-fold excess of other alkali and alkaline earth metal ions and common an-

ions like silicate, sulphate, phosphate, chlorides did not interfere. Al^{III} when present with large excess of iron could, however, be determined using DBM after removing Fe^{III} by excess of sodium hydroxide.

Experimental

Fluorescence spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer LS50B spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Bruker AC 200F spectrometer operating at (200 and 50 MHz for ^1H and ^{13}C respectively), ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 527 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on an instrument with a direct inlet system and operating at 70 eV. Thermogravimetric analysis was done on a Shimadzu DT-40 thermal analyser.

All solvents and reagents were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout.

A 1×10^{-1} M solution of DBM was prepared in ethanol. Aluminium(III) stock solution (1×10^{-1} M) was prepared by dissolving $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in distilled water containing H_2SO_4 , and standardized by EDTA¹⁰. Working standards were prepared by suitable dilution.

Aluminium dibenzoylmethane complex : To a warm (60°) solution of $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1g) in water (100 ml), DBM (2.2 g in ethanol) was added dropwise with stirring. The pH of the solution was made *ca.* 8 using 1N ammonia. The complex separated was digested at $\sim 60^\circ$ for 20 min, filtered, washed with petroleum ether and dried at 100° for 6 h over P_2O_5 under vacuum.

Procedure : Aluminium(III) solutions (1×10^{-4} M; 1–10 ml) were taken made alkaline (pH *ca.* 8) using 1N ammonia and warmed at $50\text{--}60^\circ$. Alcoholic DBM solution (1×10^{-1} M) was then added in 8-times excess. After digesting the solutions for a few minutes and cooling to room temperature, each was extracted with ethyl acetate (1 ml). Each extract was chromatographed on the Whatman paper using petroleum ether as running solvent. The reagent was thus separated from the complex, because the reagent has a quenching effect on the fluorescence of the complex. The fluorescence spot of the complex was then cut and mounted onto the dosimeter and used for measurement using right angle detection technique¹¹.

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